

THE IMPACT OF LISTENING COMPREHENSION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF OTHER LANGUAGE SKILLS

A.Saymanova

Assistant teacher at Tashkent University of Information Technologies,
Nukus branch

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship of listening skill with other skills and its influence on mastering other abilities. Nobody can deny that listening comprehension provides the right conditions for the development of other language skills. It means that the teaching of listening skills is vital in the development of other language skills. This article shows investigation done by researchers on importance of listening skill for the development of other skills for language acquisition.

Key words: listening skill, listening comprehension, interrelation.

Listening comprehension is very essential skill in the communication process that allows humans to gain insights, understanding, knowledge, and information, as well as achieving success in communicating with others. Because interpersonal communication can be established only through listening and speaking. Without listening ability social action is impossible. Broughton states that listening calls for active participation in the communication between the participants and a receptive skill is involved in understanding the message [1, p 65].

According to Stempleski, the skills of listening comprehension and pronunciation are interdependent. If language learners are not able to understand spoken English well, they cannot be understood easily, they are cut off from the language, except form the written form. In compliance to this fact, the individuals are obliged to listen to a variety of things in their daily lives. A good listener allocates 70% of his time to listening, and only 30% of his time to speaking [4, p 122].

The interrelation of speaking and listening comprehension was explained by Thanajaro who states in his research work that listening is not a passive process, but an active interrelation of four proposed activities receiving aural stimuli, attending to the spoken words, attaching meaning to the aural symbols, and responding to oral communication" [5, p 12]. These four elements are crucial for not only perceiving speech sounds, but also a whole process of attending both verbal and non-verbal expressions.

Castro also supports this idea and states that "The listening skill refers not only to the ability to comprehend sounds and different accents, but also the context and the language employed to perform the speech act [2, p 24]. Moreover, listening fosters the learning of a second language because it provides input which is a main factor in the learning process as Krashen states [3, p 64]. Based on the previous idea, learning any language requires good listening skills, as this skill allows language learners to understand and learn most aspects of the language.

The current article aimed at studying the impact of enhancing listening skill on other abilities required for language acquisition. Summarizing the research works and opinions of researchers mentioned above, it is believed that promoting listening comprehension is a key

factor in developing other language skills. Consequently, teachers should know the connection of all skills for gaining a particular language and steps of improving language skills in order to overcome possible problems in a classroom.

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